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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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***IN VITRO* APPROACHES FOR EVALUATING ANTICANCER
ACTIVITY: A COMPREHENSIVE METHODOLOGICAL REVIEW**

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Abstract: Cancer is one of the main causes of death worldwide. There were an estimated approximately 19-20 million new cases within a year, among them, breast cancer and lung cancer were highly distributed than the other types globally. Due to the high global burden caused by cancer, successful anticancer agents must be discovered and utilized. This review aims to assess the various scientific methods used to assess anticancer activity through *in vitro* techniques. This methodological review was conducted using PubMed, Google Scholar, and Hinari. We explored the databases using "anticancer activity," "*in vitro* assays," and "cell culture". The initial 135 articles were narrowed down to 55 after careful filtering based on the topic and abstract, following the PRISMA flowchart. Annual publication trends include a gradual increase in research interest over the years, beginning with a few articles found in 2014, and peaking in 2020. Notably high outputs were also observed in 2023 and 2016. The MTT (3-[4, 5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl] -2,5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide) assay was among the available methods; this is one most widely used approaches for assessing cell viability and cytotoxicity. Other often used assays include the SRB (Sulforhodamine B) assay, migration assays, flow cytometry, and polymerase chain reaction (PCR), which is crucial for assessing apoptosis and cell proliferation studies. The variety of *in vitro* techniques used to evaluate anticancer potential in laboratory settings is further demonstrated by the frequent use of techniques like live/dead staining, trypan blue exclusion assay, and colony-forming assays. *In vitro* anticancer tests offer important information on the biological and cytotoxic effects of medicinal substances. *In vitro* anticancer assays provide a valuable tool for potential therapeutic agents while minimizing the need for animal experimentation. Compared to *in vivo* techniques, these methods offer a more ethical, cost-effective, and rapid approach to preliminary screening.

Keywords: Anticancer Activity; Cell Culture; *In vitro* Assay; MTT Assay

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